

Socio-Psychological Principles of Image in Commander's Activity

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the topic of psychological principles of image in the activity of the commander. Also, all theoretical analyzes and scientific considerations and phenomena concepts related to determining the purpose of the problem are covered based on the sources provided in the list of literature.

Keywords: commander, military occupational activity, image, professional military, national defense, army, soldier, war, military action, officer, military team, military courage, national pride, national identity.

As it is known, one of the priorities of the national defense system is the implementation of a number of socio-economic and legal reforms. The current ethnic identity and future, power and reputation of the national army, the modern army and its national image, military activities, modern military personnel, military professional activities, professional skills, professions and personalities, psychological aspects of military professional activities are one of the most important scientific papers waiting for the psychological solution in the defense system[1,4].

From a scientific point of view, military service is not only a social issue, but also a kind of human activity that depends on special circumstances. Motherland's protection is always the highest honor for every citizen. The army is always considered part of society, in its essence reflects all the socio-economic and political processes in society, as well as all the laws of the international situation[2,23].

According to the researcher A.Rostunov, military professional activity is the protection of Motherland. It contains many components. First of all, it involves two main types of activities, namely combat situations and simplicity. Military activity is the activity of many military personnel in achieving the goals of war[3,67].

It should be noted that combat operations are very specific in terms of their goals, objectives, means, difficulties and psychological content. In other words, these movements are the result of such complex tasks as the socio-psychological laws, internal structure and goals of military-political, military, technical, ideological and socio-psychological, weapons, team leadership, educational work carried out in combat operations, combat and psychological training of military personnel is described[4,331].

These complex tasks are likely to affect the psychological structure and composition of combat activities, which are self-destructive, life-threatening, loss of people and equipment, and the various deprivations and disadvantages. It requires a clear implementation of warfare tasks, ie

high level of ethical and legal responsibility. Such actions can cause excessive mental and physical tension in the military.

As mentioned above, any humanitarian activity has its purpose. No more fighting actions. As for the cause of military action at the state level, the main reason is the threat to the integrity and security of the country. The meaning of such actions also implies the existence of military personnel in military operations. There are a number of psychological reasons for the military's military operations: needs, emotions, wishes, aspirations, interests, ideals, beliefs, etc. [5,132].

The researcher V.Suvorov noted that the most important necessity for fighting is the wish of survival. This is a normal, genetic aspect for self-defense, and it is definite. But it is manifested in different ways for all people and can have different consequences for a person and social environment. One person manages active and targeted military technology and combat methods because he understands better that a well-trained person can survive the war. At the same time, during the war, the other person strives to avoid dangerous situations and hide behind his comrades, that is, he is cowardly [6,123].

The following questions need to be answered: If the self-defense mechanism is biological, codified, and reasoned, why do thousands of heroes in history and martyrs who sacrificed themselves for their homeland, and what led to their self-sacrifice? In fact, it is desirable to take into consideration not only the biological, but also the social needs of a person, being a social person. Because people's military action is not in the biological context for social needs.

The most important socio-psychological causes of military action are the protection of their homeland, their families and their relatives. That is why thousands have sacrificed themselves for a common victory during World War II. This motto is socially-psychologically that it does not arise in human beings since birth, but in the process of its development and social development. It is manifested in various movements of the person, and it is manifested in ideologies and beliefs. Therefore, the main task of each military officer is to instill feelings of patriotism, national pride, national pride and loyalty to the young soldiers.

It is important to note that any activity has specific goals. Through the practice of the war, the soldiers achieve their near and far-reaching goals. The main purpose of combat operations is to defeat the enemy and to overcome it. Achieving the goals in the battle takes place in certain conditions that reflect the nature of the war, in danger of surprises and strong influences. That's why combat operations are a complex form of clear-cut cooperation between the military and the military. The researcher of the great military heroes and modern military man, S. Burda, believes that the military has to take into account the combat situation, take into account possible changes, eliminate adverse effects, and possess high knowledge and ability to use weapons, it is necessary to have a high level of combat capabilities and qualities. In carrying out their assignments, each soldier must anticipate the possible course and outcome of tactical actions, compare it with what he has, observe the situation, and take every case from creativity standpoint [7,52].

It should be noted that the change in any operating environment leads to the "launch" of adaptive mechanisms that ensure adaptive action. Military activities are also distinguished by adaptation mechanisms on their own, but full compliance with war conditions never happens because human life cannot withstand a constant threat. Sooner or later, adaptation to combat situations must be encouraged. For some people this is too early, and for others it is too late.

The emergence of new weapons in the context of globalization led to the complication of hostilities, which, in turn, set high requirements for the achievement of the objectives of the Armed Forces and the professional, ethical and spiritual training of the servicemen. Therefore, it is necessary to study the socio-psychological conditions of military service efficiency determination and reliability. In the field of defense theory and practice, each potential military

officer must know how the war influences people's spirit, how to control their behavior in fighting situations, prevent and eliminate uncertainty, and how fear and self-sacrifice affect the human psychology is considered to be. Studying the socio-psychological aspects of combat movements, spiritual readiness for the soldiers, psychological models of modern combat operations, and so on.

Another type of military-technical activity is military activity, which operates in normal and peaceful conditions. At first glance, it is impossible to notice a significant difference in personal activity before joining the Armed Forces or contracting service. But such thinking is wrong. A young man who wants to serve on a military service or on a contract basis is forced to abandon his usual morality. It is related to the specific features of military service. Long-term military serviceman is an important person in the modern armed forces. The level of professional training of long-term military servicemen, in particular, defines the ability of the Motherland to solve complex and different tasks. Therefore, all developed countries of the world are keen to improve the quality of their vocational training for long-term military personnel and offer their recommendations.

Modern long-term military personnel are very professional. In the military-professional activities of servicemen there are several main areas of service: the management of the military personnel; staff training and continuous improvement of their professional skills and knowledge.

From a psychological point of view, activity is described as a kind of human activity, including the knowledge and artistic transformation of the universe, specifically to itself and to its present circumstances. Human activity, once practiced, is manifested as a material activity. Any activity is usually based on one or more motives or goals and a series of actions that are specifically targeted.

The activity is always related to specific needs, which indicates that the subject needs something and its need reflects the action of action. Obedience, assimilation, determinants of activity by the outside world. In the process of assimilation, the needs of the subject, its objectiveness, are converted to specific activities. In the future, the object's activity is determined by the image, not the object itself, but in the search conditions.

Insufficient personal knowledge and skills are essential to achieving self-awareness. Emotional stability in a person is a condition of socio-psychological knowledge. It is known in the research that professionalism and superiority are related to the moral and emotional features of a person[8,172].

The main socio-psychological lines of military professional activity are also explained by: relationships between military service and military duty; studying and adapting military equipment; performing combat functions and improving the quality of self-sacrifice, and so on.

The professional military or military activity is characterized by the following: a warrior knows the high duties assigned to him; targets and development of future action plans; high level of equipment and equipment; able to regulate all actions according to the high functions.

According to the subjective-psychological point of view, there are collective character in the current group movements. The leader or the leader should always be respectful of his subjects, understand others' goals, maintain a positive psychological climate in the community, and be an example to others in military superiority and discipline[9,89]. Military team members are also characterized by their unique attributes.

The Russian psychologist B.M.Teplov said that three key qualities of the commander must have been formed equal, for instance, mind, emotion, will. If one of the three most important

qualities are weak, such a soldier will be defeated in battle. Because, when dealing with different tactics in the fight, it is necessary to leave the enemy laugh, willpower is a factor of self-control in patience, endurance and during the most difficult times. Emotion is a psychological internal mechanism that destroys fear, agility, warlike or negative feelings in this soldier [10,147].

The names of those who have such qualities can be seen in many studies. For example, Iosif Vissarionov, Mikhail Kutuzov, Georgiy Jukov from the Russian heroes, Amir Temur, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Pahlavon Mahmud, our great heroes, are exemplary examples of this.

In summary, the socio-psychological aspects of military-professional activities include the explanation of a number of phenomena that are present in the soldier's personality, such as dedication, social consciousness, national pride, national honor, high duty, national identity and national identity; but also scientific research.

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